

Rac-7b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	x1-3-153-4-RAC-20%-IF	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	104	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 154 4 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/29/2022 4:14:43 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/29/2022 4:52:39 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.082	3296466	51.23	307849
2	8.765	3137834	48.77	279656

Asy-7b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	x1-3-153-4-ASY-20%-IF	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	22	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 153 4 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/29/2022 4:33:55 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/29/2022 4:50:46 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.082	2634525	95.80	256544
2	8.772	115364	4.20	11976